

Data Management Plan

Version 1.0

MoSTFun — Monitoring Strategies and Tools to address knowledge gaps on aquatic Fungal biodiversity

Funding Acknowledgement: This document is based upon work from MoSTFun project, funded by Biodiversa+, the European Biodiversity Partnership under the 2022–2023 BiodivMon joint call for research proposals, co-funded by the European Commission (GA N°101052342) and with the funding organisations: The Swiss National Science Foundation (31BD30_216821), The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (2023-00070), The Research Council of Norway (350971), the Spanish Fundación Biodiversidad, Italian Ministry of University and Research (BIODIV22_00081), Estonian Research Council (SLTTI24220), German Research Foundation (GR 1540/52-1); and the Indianapolis Zoo, USA.

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1. FRAMEWORK & SCOPE

1.1 Administrative information

Project MoSTFun: MONITORING STRATEGIES FOR AQUATIC FUNGI BIODIVERSITY

Responsible MoSTFun Data Management Committee (DMC)

Milestone M3. Data Management Plan (DMP)

Work package WP6 Management Coordination

Delivery date 23 August 2024

Availability Public

Data Management Plan version history

Version	Date	Modification	Author(s)
0.0	29 June 2024	Original version	DMC
0.1	24 Aug 2024	Internal Proof	DM

DMC - Data and Digital Outputs Management Committee

Country	DMC member	Active date (start)
Estonia	Victoria Prins	September 2024
Germany	Jason Woodhouse*	April 2024
Italy	Emanuele Ferrari	April 2024
Norway	Teppo Rama	April 2024
Spain	Albert Reñé	April 2024
Sweden	Jennifer Anderson	April 2024
Switzerland	Red Calore	May 2024

*Committee Chair

Past members:

1.2 Scope:

The DMP

- supports common understanding and expectations among Partners and associated teams for the management of data associated with MoSTFun.
- serves as a tool to ensure MoSTFun meets research community, partner institution, national and EU standards for data access (inclusive of FAIR principles and deposition of data into appropriate public repositories).
- provides a mutually agreed framework defining the use, sharing, and storage of data.

1.3 Acronyms, abbreviations, and definitions

Text	Reference
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMC	Data Management Committee
DMP	Data Management Plan
EDC	Engagement and Dissemination Committee
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EO	Earth Observation (e.g. Satellite)
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GBIF	<i>Global Biodiversity Information Facility</i>
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
SC	Steering Committee
PrID	Project unique identifier
SSID	Sample specific identifier

2. DATA MANAGEMENT COMMITTEE

2.1 Authority for formation

MoSTFun uses the management structure described in the funded project proposal wherein responsibilities are delegated among three committees, the Steering Committee (SC), Engagement and Dissemination Committee (EDC) and Data Management Committee (DMC). The formation of the DMC is thus authorized.

In its inception the roles of the DMC were defined as follows:

“The role of the DMC is to establish transparent sample and data sharing rules with each stakeholder and according to internationally accepted standards.” -- Section V.A.

The DMC “...will include three team members from different partners with experience in data handling and database management. The DMC will be tasked with establishing transparent data sharing rules with each stakeholder and ensuring adherence to the data sharing rules of each data source used in this study. The DMC is also responsible for adherence and reporting to satisfy requirements of the Nagoya protocol and to ensure FAIR principles for resulting data.” -- Section V.C

“The DMC will develop a Data Management Plan (DMP) to ensure data access and re-use according to the FAIR data principles, toward the concept of Open Data and Open Science, as foreseen by EU Open Science Policy.” -- Section V.F.

2.2 Membership, responsibilities, and scope

DMC will develop, implement, and update an operational MoSTFun Data and Digital Outputs Management Plan, support adherence to the DMP, and ensure the MoSTFun DMP meets research community, partner institution, national and EU standards. The DMC has the following membership structure and additional specific responsibilities.

- The membership of the DMC was amended through a vote of all partners to comprise at least one team member (where possible) from each different partner institutions. See page 1 for membership record.
- DMC is tasked with establishing transparent data sharing rules with each stakeholder and ensuring adherence to the data sharing rules of each data source used in this study
- The DMC is responsible for oversight of project adherence and reporting relevant to the Nagoya Protocol.
- The DMC is responsible for ensuring data access and re-use according to FAIR principles.

3. DATA DESCRIPTIONS & EXPECTED DIGITAL OUTPUTS

3.1 Purpose of data collection

Data collection and research are in accordance with the MoSTFun Project Plan. The goals of the project are available online:

- Project webpage MOSTFUN.eu (www.mostfun.eu)
- Biodiversa+, 2022-2023 Call BiodivMon (<https://www.biodiversa.eu/2024/04/15/mostfun/>)

3.2 Data types collected

Raw observational data

Primarily text and numerical. Text here refers largely to DNA sequence data and predefined metadata. Numerical data includes outputs of chemical analyses and environmental descriptors (e.g. temperature, pH, latitude, longitude). Images will be taken as part of the documentation of the sampling sites (metadata & communications materials), but are not planned for direct analysis. Publicly available Earth Observation (EO) data will also be accessed.

Personal data

Names, professional titles, phone numbers and email addresses of Stakeholders. See APPENDIX 1 for Information for Data Subjects, contact information, and storage details. These data are collected for the sole purpose of Stakeholder engagement and communication as defined in the project plan on the legal basis of Public Interest. Stakeholders may have the right to have their information erased, corrected or limited. Their rights can be exerted by contacting the authorities indicated in APPENDIX 1. This list will not be shared or made public without the consent of the Stakeholders. This information will be stored in a secure non-cloud-based server with restricted access.

Personal data for MoSTFun Partners and Teams will be collected inclusive of name, affiliation, country, work email address, CV (e.g. of Partners as part of application process), photo (voluntary), social media handles (voluntary). This information is necessary for internal use to support communications and official reporting. Additional use of personal data is strictly with approval of the person(s) and may include acknowledgement of participation in the project on the website MOSTFUN.eu, on X (or any other social media platforms), and in acknowledgement slides.

Photos

Photos collected within the project will be matched with the name of the photographer through the file naming convention, ensuring correct attribution for the photographer. By submitting photos to the project directories, it is understood by MoSTFun participants that their name will be public as the photo credit if/when their photos are used for MoSTFun presentations, publications, and communications to support correct and transparent attribution of credit.

In the case of photos that include people, they can only be submitted to the project if expressed permission from those pictured is provided. The initials of the person/people must be reported through the naming convention and their full name included in the file MOSTFUN_photos_README. The photographer is responsible for ensuring that every pictured person understands that their photo and name (optional) will be public if/ when the photos are used for MoSTFun presentations, publications, and communications.

DNA

DNA extracted from MoSTFun samples as well as archive samples obtained from third parties will be stored in Sweden and/or at the Partner institutions, as appropriate for the intended uses of the DNA. The location of the DNA sample will be recorded as within- MoSTFun metadata to keep track of the sample.

Biological samples – MoSTFun

Samples obtained for DNA extraction during MoSTFun sampling, including water, sediment, and plant litter (where applicable) will be stored according to agreed project protocols by the Partner institutions, at -20°C, or room temperature (depending on the agreed storage buffer) before transport to Estonia for DNA extraction.

Water samples for inorganic nutrients analyses from MoSTFun sampling will be stored at -20°C at the Partner institutions, and transported frozen to Servicios de Seguridad Alimentaria y Desarrollo Sostenible del Centro de Apoyo Científico Tecnológico a la Investigación (C.A.C.T.I.) - Universidad de Vigo (Spain) for analysis. The location of the samples will be recorded as within-MoSTFun metadata to keep track of the sample.

Biological samples – third party

Water, sediment, plant material and filters for DNA extraction obtained from third parties will be collected by the Partner Institutions. The samples will be codified according to the MoSTFun naming convention, and their metadata will be collected and stored. The samples will be preserved in the freezer, and transported to Estonia/Sweden for their further analysis.

Stakeholder Survey Data

Information from stakeholders will be collected through provided surveys. Stakeholders survey will include, beside data on the compiler, questions useful to characterize the type of stakeholder the compiler is representing, and questions of the contribution the Institution/Project/Infrastructure/etc. the compiler is representing to MOSTFUN, as detailed below. The main goal of the surveys will be to implement the network of people and Institution interested in MOSTFUN project, to engage into synergistic approach aimed at raising awareness on the importance of AF and the potential engage with existing project.

Personal information from Stakeholders

Personal information of the compiler of the survey will be collected and stored as specified in the paragraph “3.2 Personal data”. In addition, for Webinar registration the following information will be collected: name, last name, email, job title, country/region, organization, registration time, approval, status. The data will be used to generate general statistical information and the private information will be stored in a sharepoint file at SLU for a maximum of 1 year after the end of the project.

Data from the project that Stakeholder manage

Data and samples that will be asked from stakeholders have already been collected in the frame of previous projects and research. Most of these data/metadata/samples are also described in datapapers and deposited in official repositories, or deposited alongside specific publication. Data and samples will be collected and stored according to the regulations imposed by the Nagoya protocol for signaturing countries, GDPR, and in compliance with national and international regulations. As an EU project, MOSTFUN will inform stakeholders willing to share data and samples on the purpose of reusing and sharing the data in accordance with the FAIR principles, as described in paragraph 7. Failure to adhere or to accept implications of the FAIR principle will prevent the stakeholders from participating in the project. All data will be stored in official certified repositories. We will target primarily Figshare, GBIF, GeneBank, OSF, and Zenodo. Data will be largely described in associated data papers.

Respondents will be informed about the purpose of this study on the first page of the survey and they will be asked to agree to participate in this study via an OK button. Data will be collected and stored in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as specified in chapter 6. We will collect only limited personal information from respondents, to verify that the information comes from a trustworthy source or to give information about collaboration efforts and snowballing purposes. The information collected in the survey will be: name of the project, type of the project, type of ecosystem involved, countries covered by the project, years covered by the project, name of the contact person and email address, and finally condition for use of data/samples.

Digital products

Archives including internal management documents and minutes produced during the project life-time will be stored in a Directory called Consortium Meetings, located within the internally shared MosTFun Google Drive. Project outputs including survey texts, guidelines, protocols, scripts, workflows, reports, outreach material and policy briefs will be produced and published in public repositories when/if needed. The files will be preserved in appropriate standard formats to ensure their longevity and interoperability, making them as FAIR as possible.

3.3 Expected data sizes

The amount of data generated depends in large part on which sequencing technologies are available at the time of sample submission. MoSTFun is prepared for the secure storage of 1-2 Tb of raw sequence data. This can be expanded with need. Sampling photos, and potentially films, are tentatively expected to require up to 100 Gb. Estimation of expected data sizes is ongoing.

3.4 Expected datasets & outputs of long-term value

Description	WP	Public availability (upon publication when applicable)
Sample metadata from global repositories, existing collections, sampling programs	1,5	Zenodo
Database of aquatic fungal metabarcode and genome sequences from existing resources	1,4	Zenodo, GlobalFungi, Mgnify (EMBL),
18S- and ITS-rDNA metabarcode sequences from archival/new samples	1, 2	UNITE, Mgnify (EMBL), GlobalFungi
Species/OTU distributions	1, 2	PlutoF, GBIF
Sequences of anti-fungal resistance genes	1, 2	European Nucleotide Archive
Water physical-chemical datasets	1, 2	PlutoF
Ecosystem processes data	2	MoSTFun website, Zenodo
EO and GIS metadata	3	Zenodo, Github
Scripts and workflows	1, 2, 3, 4	Zenodo, Github
Outreach, Reports, Policy briefs, surveys, guidelines, protocols	3, 4, 5	MoSTFun website, Zenodo
Management documents	6	MoSTFun website, Zenodo
Scientific papers	1, 2, 3, 4	Published open access

4. DATA COLLECTION

4.1 MoSTFun -generated primary data types and timing

Primary (raw) data generated by MoSTFun is accumulated but not otherwise changed. The timing of data collection is estimated and subject to change. This section pertains specifically to new sample collections performed by MoSTFun or on behalf of MoSTFun and their associated metadata, sequence data, etc. and also to MoSTFun generated new data from 3rd party archival samples.

- Sample metadata: Collection of sample metadata, particularly from archival samples, will be ongoing but commence in August 2024 and increase over winter 2024 and 2025.
- 18S- and ITS-rDNA metabarcode sequence: Sequencing will be performed at SciLife Lab, Uppsala (Sweden). Archival samples identified through freezer-surveys (WP1) will be compiled in the first half of 2025 with sequencing expected that year. Additional sampling to fill gaps, e.g. in estuaries, coastal and alpine areas, will be performed throughout 2025 with sequence data expected to be generated in early 2026.
- Metagenome datasets: Additional sequencing of selected samples will be performed to identified genes involved in anti-fungicide resistance. Sequencing is expected to be completed in the first half of 2026.
- Water chemistry datasets: Chemical analyses will be performed by Servicios de Seguridad Alimentaria y Desarrollo Sostenible del Centro de Apoyo Científico Tecnológico a la Investigación (C.A.C.T.I.) de la Universidad de Vigo (SSADS-CACTI), Spain. Data will be generated in batches with the bulk of the data for WP1 and WP2 coming by autumn 2024.

4.2 Secondary data

Secondary (derivative) and Working datasets and storage fall under the responsibility of the RPs with guidance from the DMC. These datasets are typically derived from analysis pipelines and can be recreated from primary data by applying analysis/analyses, pipelines, or scripts. End products of these processes that are relied upon for reports/publications/etc... and scripts will be made public as per 3.4 (inclusive of details of their derivation).

Secondary data in MoSTFun also includes pre-existing data associated with the archival samples that is obtained from the associated Stakeholder or database (e.g. site information, water chemistry information, other measures produced by the Stakeholder).

4.3 Other data

Primary data from FUNACTION and FunAqua will be included in MoSTFun. Data was independently generated by the Estonian partner before formation of FUNACTION, and both projects pre-date MoSTFun. FunAqua and FUNACTION also have independent funding histories, which can include obligations for acknowledgements of funding etc. The

producers of this data are within MoSTFun, but in the interest of maintaining proper credit, attribution, and use, we recognize this within the DMP.

Other public datasets will be used in the course of analysis, e.g. environmental data, EO data, reference sequence data. Data use will be acknowledged and follow source-specific rules.

Stakeholder information will be collected from MoSTFun participants (their individual networks), internet searches of publicly available information, and through a snowball approach where interested stakeholders are asked to suggest other relevant stakeholders. This process began during grant preparation and is expected to continue through project month 24.

Photos will be taken as part of documentation of sampling sites and campaigns. These images are collected in a central directory on KoboToolbox and backed up to Google Drive together with appropriate metadata. Metadata is recorded in the file name according to the standards described within the DMP, with the addition of a unique code or name to identify the photographer (to support attribution of the image) and any people included in the photo.

Internal Committee Archives will be maintained by each MoSTFun committee inclusive of decisions and documents of value. It is anticipated that these archives will be most useful during the project and within 1 year of the project end. The archives will be populated, maintained, and stored by a designated member of each committee such that they are accessible to the committee and full consortium. The archives must be backed up to a physical computer or server by that designated member regularly.

5. DATA IDENTIFIERS

As part of its conceptualisation MoSTFun leverages data generated from existing aquatic fungal biodiversity research programs, namely FunAqua and FUNACTION. Outside of the framework of these projects MoSTFun will also analyze archived (freezer and digital) samples that might have their own specific identifiers (e.g. ENA Accession numbers).

To this end MoSTFun has chosen to adopt a two-level naming scheme, incorporating a MoSTFun project unique identifier (PrID) and a sample specific identifier (SSID) that is applicable to both new samples, which require assignment of a PrID and SSID, and existing archival samples for which a SSID exists but a PrID should be assigned.

5.1 Project unique ID (PrID)

PrIDs are an eight character alphanumeric barcode consisting of MF-PartnerID(1)-(5 numeric)

Partner	Partner ID
SUPSI	1
MEG - IRSA	2
IGB	3
SLU	4
UiT (Rama)	5
UniTartu	6
ICM - CSIC	7
UiT (Frainer)	8
Indianapolis Zoo Center for Species Survival*	A

*Samples from this partner are not anticipated

Assignment of the PrID to each sample should be performed by the responsible partner with the 5 remaining digits decided by each project partner. For example:

SUPSI has been assigned PrID MF100001-MF199999 inclusive.

To ensure consistency, each RPs are responsible for assigning a MoSTFun PrID to each archived sample, making use of the PrID naming convention, site data collection survey (4.1) and available metadata from the stakeholders. MoSTFun employs a two-level naming convention project unique identifiers (PrID) throughout, from sample collection to

publication and associated datasets. All samples, datasets, sample submissions, raw data, photos, etc... must follow the agreed PrID structure.

5.2 Sample-specific Site ID (SSID):

The USID is the base name for all samples collected at a specific site and specific sampling occasion. As already stated, USID for existing samples (FunAqua, FUNACTION and others) should remain unaltered. For new samples taken as part of MoSTFun, USID should be assigned in accordance with sample metadata and the scheme outlined below (See components Table 5.1 and 5.2). Sample type and replicate are specified on the sampling container and all derived data(sets).The SSID is flexible and can include additional information (e.g. data type or state) to accommodate identification of derivative data(sets).

Table 5.1 Components of the USID and ST and their accepted values.

SSID	Description
GID:	Geographic ID, describing the general geographic context (e.g. AC, Artic coastline)
SID:	Site ID. number assigned to a specific site and <u>always re-used for that specific site</u> . If collecting in different teams, assign a different range of numbers for use by the different teams to avoid duplication. USE ## format for best machine readability. So for numbers 1-9, USE 01-09.
SO:	Sampling occasion. If a site is visited for the first time and/or the only time, it gets T1. Increase the # to denote the 2nd, 3rd etc. collection for temporal sampling.
ST:	Sample type

Table 5.2 Components of the USID and ST and their accepted values.

	Unique Site ID (USID)			Specific Sample types (ST)			
	Broad geographic ID	Site ID (SID)	Sampling occasion (SO)	Sterivex filter	Chemistry (water for chemical analysis)	Sediment	Litter
MoSTFun/ FUNACTION (WP2/WP2)	GID Table 5.3	## 01-30	T1-T8	W1, W2	C1, C2	S	L

6. Metadata (minimal information requirements)

In addition to the information embedded in the PrID, samples incorporated into MoSTFun will require a minimum set of metadata, consistent with FAIR principles (Appendix 2).

Within MoSTFun, metadata mostly, but not exclusively, refers to information pertaining to samples and/or sequence data obtained directly or via stakeholders. Given the non-standardised sampling/sequencing methodology that we expect across samples it is critical that such method specific information is also collected and maintained.

7. DATA SECURITY, STORAGE & COSTS

7.1 During the project period

Non-personal data backup at SUPSI Backup copies of non-personal data will be stored as follows to prevent data loss and data security. Secure data storage (managed by the SLU university IT platform) with replication to offsite backup for the project period + 1 year. Direct access is limited to registered participants at SLU and data transferred to outside partners as needed using SFTP or via restricted access sharing via the MoSTFun Community on [Zenodo](#).

Google drive: MoSTFun has a shared directory on Google Drive. Use of this product shall be controlled through the sharing options on the site to be visible and editable only to/by those invited to participate in the directory and shall be limited as follows:

- To include only non-sensitive and reproducible (or sufficiently backed-up) data. Personal data shall NOT be stored on Google Drive without the informed consent of the parties involved.
- Primarily for purposes of active collaboration.

Partner institutions: Partners, with the support of the DMC and DMP, are required to ensure the responsible backup of local and derived datasets that cannot be reasonably re-derived from scripts or pipelines through their Institutions and/or other reasonable and effective alternatives and following the principles herein (7.1). Reasonable and effective alternatives depend on data type and may include a restricted access Community at [Zenodo](#), [GitHub](#), etc. after approval from the DMC.

7.2 Long-term

Deposit of MoSTFun data in recognized public data repositories is a priority. Data and other digital outputs will be made available (see 3.4) following FAIR standards as per 7 DATA USE AND SHARING, herein.

Terms of use, data security, privacy, and other restrictions upon publication or official release of digital data and outputs follow the terms of use of the individual databases and

are beyond the scope and control of MoSTFun. The databases are selected based on community standards, reliability, and limited restrictions.

MoSTFun partner institutions and funders have varying approaches/requirements for data archiving. Partners, with the support of their local member of the DMC, are responsible for meeting institutional and funder data storage and archiving responsibilities in addition to the terms herein.

7.3 Costs

Costs for the safe storage of primary data are assumed by Partner 1 (Coordinator) at SUPSI, other costs are assumed by the Partners. Budgeted costs cover secure storage of 2 TB with backup to a secondary site for 4 years. This extends 1 year past the project duration to ensure adequate opportunity for all data to be submitted to online repositories. Partners assume responsibility for their local costs of data backup, security and storage of primary data copies, secondary data and scripts.

7.4 Data Organization

Primary data: Directory structure and naming conventions will be established and updated by the DMC prioritizing FAIR principles and making use of public advice e.g. the following:

- [File Naming Conventions](#) from Longwood Research Data Management, Harvard.
- [File Naming](#) from ELIXIR-Belgium.

Directory and file names are expected to use the PrID when applicable (5 DATA IDENTIFIERS). Updating and version control of these datasets will be coordinated by the DMC.

Secondary data: These data are generated at Partner institutions and must adhere to Institutional requirements for Directory structure and naming conventions where applicable. To share these data among Partners (directly, via Zenodo Community or other) or with other approved recipients, the conventions for primary data must be applied.

7.5 Responsibility for data

Primary data: Directory structure and naming conventions will be established and updated by the DMC prioritizing FAIR principles and making use of public advice e.g. the following:

- [File Naming Conventions](#) from Longwood Research Data Management, Harvard.
- [File Naming](#) from ELIXIR-Belgium.

Directory and file names are expected to use the PrID when applicable (5 DATA IDENTIFIERS).

8. DATA USE & SHARING

8.1 General principles

MoSTFun datasets will be formatted and made accessible at the time of publication or before (see Criteria for external pre-publication sharing) according to the community standards as follows:

FAIR: Described briefly here. Visit [GO FAIR](#) for details and advice.

Findable: at the appropriate time (below) data will be deposited in public data repositories with globally unique persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI) and linked to technical, sample and site-associated metadata. Where appropriate, sample metadata will be organized in CSV format, uploaded and managed by the community standard databases.

Accessible: Datasets will not require proprietary tools for access and access support is available through database/repository websites.

Interoperable: for the (meta)data, standardized formats and terminologies will be used to the extent possible and explanatory documentation provided in the linked readme.txt files.

Reusable: All samples will receive identifiers specifying the location, date and substrate, that will be used with all associated metadata and sequences ensuring traceability from field to database and interconnectivity among resulting datasets.

8.2 Within project data & digital output sharing

Primary data: Sequence data, physico-chemical data, land-use data, and other metadata will be produced through or by individual Partner institutions with direct registration (KoboToolbox, 4.1) to a shared site and/or prompt transfer of a digital copy of the raw data for backup at SLU. Copies of the raw data may also be made available within MoSTFun as described in 6.1 During the project period.

The coordinator and DMC representative of Sweden has/have access to datasets at SLU and will provide data to Partners promptly upon request with the following exception.

In the unforeseen case that a request is made for data that is outside the scope of a Partner's project responsibilities (as defined by roles and expectations in the MoSTFun application), the request will be evaluated by the DMC prior to data availability. Access will be granted if all of the following are true:

- Providing the data is consistent with and advances progress towards MoSTFun goals and objectives.
- Access to the data does not infringe on other Partners rights and responsibilities within the project.
- Co-authorships, collaborations, or other fair and transparent arrangements are formally (by email to DMC) and mutually pre-agreed.

Secondary data: These data are generated at partner institutions and are expected to be available among MoSTFun participants following the same principles and criteria as for Primary Data (above) but sharing is managed by the RP and/or RP designated responsible

(e.g. national DMC representative). Sharing can be achieved by any secure method unless otherwise noted as excluded by the DMC and future versions of the DMP).

Outreach and engagement materials (digital): With the exception of sensitive information, these materials can and should be freely shared within MoSTFun. The EDC and DMC shall cooperate to ensure and encourage sharing and use of such materials.

8.3 Public access to data and digital outputs

Scientific papers: MoSTFun prioritizes publishing open access. Papers will be made publicly available from the time of publication. By mutual agreement among authors, the pre-publication version may be made publicly available via a field-appropriate and recognized pre-print archive.

Data that is the basis of Scientific papers: To support publication, datasets relied on for scientific papers will be deposited in public repositories (see 3.4 Expected datasets & outputs of long-term value) following the guidelines herein (e.g. 7.1 General principles) and made publicly available upon formal publication (does not include pre-review or pre-print versions).

The lead author and corresponding author of each manuscript is responsible for coordinating with the DMC and other work groups and authors to ensure that the data access is made public upon publication.

Outreach & engagement materials (digital): These outputs will be released to the public annually or earlier at the discretion of the DMC in cooperation with the EDC when they meet all criteria below.

Note: Publication to the [MOSTFUN.eu](https://mostfun.eu) website and social media accounts can occur at any time—and is primarily at the discretion of the EDC but cannot conflict with restrictions within the DMP. Stakeholder names and contact information WILL NOT be shared (unless informed voluntary consent is documented) but stakeholders may be identified by organization name if necessary (as determined by the EDC).

- Making the output public is consistent with and advances progress towards MoSTFun goals and objectives.
- Access to output does not infringe on other Partners rights and responsibilities within the project.
- Attributions are correctly and transparently acknowledged.
- The materials have been verified to meet GDPR expectations.

8.4 Criteria for external pre-publication sharing

MoSTFun aims to produce the best possible scientific, societal, and policy outcomes. MoSTFun also has strong interests in capacity building and amplifying the impact of the project through building additional collaborations and supporting scientific and policy endeavors more broadly. To meet these ambitions, it can be in the best interests of MoSTFun to share data with non-MoSTFun participants before publication.

Partners shall request permissions for external pre-publication data sharing from the DMC in writing. Requests shall be evaluated within 14 days according to the criteria below.

Partners shall be informed of such requests by their representative on the DMC and have the opportunity to express their views through their representative. Decisions by the DMC will be made in writing, inclusive of brief descriptions of how the three criteria are met or fail to be met by the request and any restrictions for use. The written decision shall become part of the DMCs archive.

9. Ethical Concerns

9.1 Compliance with Nagoya Protocols

The exchange of genetic material and sequence data between partner and stakeholder nations necessitates all partner organisations to respect the ethical frameworks of Convention on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya protocol.

In accordance with this framework EU member nations can refer to the published “Guidance document on the scope of application and core obligations of Regulation (EU) No 511/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the compliance measures for users from the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilisation in the Union (2021/C 13/01)”.

Within this document it states that:

“Identification of a genetic resource is also to be considered to precede utilisation. Taxonomic identification of biological or genetic material, by morphological or molecular analysis, including through use of DNA sequencing, is not considered to constitute utilisation in the meaning of the EU ABS Regulation, as it does not involve the discovery of specific genetic and/or biochemical functionality”

Within this context, obtaining samples and sequence data for purely taxonomic description of fungal species (WP1,2), which constitutes almost all of the methodological approaches within MoSTFun, would be exempt.

However, the description of anti-fungal resistance genes, and other trait encoding genes within the genomes of fungi or otherwise aquatic microorganisms (metagenomics) is subject to the articles of the Nagoya protocol, due to their ability to be exploited for commercial gain.

As such any transfer of material between partners from stakeholders to partners will be performed in compliance with the Nagoya Protocol. All EU member institutions are within signatory nations, and fall under the EU ABS Regulation. Our US partner is not a signatory to the Nagoya Protocols and this should be a consideration for material transfer. Specificities on the ABS process will be determined for each origin country. For data coming from Switzerland, the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) will be informed of the usage of the data/samples through the appropriate form as requested from the Swiss ABS regulation. Moreover, the metadata generated for each sample will be stored for as long as required by FOEN.

10. APPENDIX 1: DATA HANDLING DOCUMENTATION

Working draft

Information to data subjects about the processing of personal data in MoSTFun. Each partner organisation is expected to sign an agreement that assumes responsibility of Joint Controllership. This ensures that all partner organisations that have access to GDPR compliant personal data stored at the SLU are responsible for ensuring its security.

Joint Data Controllers

The Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU). The data protection officer at SLU can be reached at dataskydd@slu.se.

Others to be added upon completion of Joint Controllership Agreement or Joint Processor Agreement

Purpose

We are undertaking research supported by public funds. As part of the MoSTFunproject, it is necessary to identify, communicate with, invite to stakeholder events, and/or seek feedback from parties (stakeholders) that might have interest in the work, be impacted by the work, and/or who can influence the work, as this is in the public interest.

Categories of personal data and sources

First name, last name, title and work or professional email address and phone number for representatives of governmental authorities, companies, non-profit organizations. First name, last name, and preferred email address for interested citizens who voluntarily provide this information and have requested communications on the project. Coordinates of sample sites are also collected.

Legal basis

Public Interest. This personal data processing is necessary in order to fulfill a task of Public Interest. This research has been funded by the EU as well as each individual partner state for the researchers involved.

The principle of public access to information

SLU and Partner Institutions that are public authorities, must apply the principle of public access to official documents. This means that all official documents, including personal data, that are not considered working material are public and can be released to anyone who requests them. However, if a document contains data that is subject to confidentiality, the document will not be released.

Storing data

Your personal data will be stored on a secure server at SLU. Data access is restricted to authorized individuals from the Partner Institutions. Your data will be stored until the latest 31 March 2027, one year past the project end point, to allow completion of project related tasks.

Your personal data will also be stored for as long as required by the Public Access to Information Act and the regulations on the archives of public authorities.

Your rights

You have the right, under certain circumstances, to have your personal data erased, corrected or limited. You also have the right of access to the personal data being processed, and you have the right to object to the processing of your data. To exert your rights, contact dataskydd@slu.se.

Comments: If you have any comments on the processing of personal data at SLU, contact dataskydd@slu.se.

If you are not happy with the answer provided by SLU, you can take your complaint to the Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection, imy@imy.se or +46 (0)8-657 61 00.

Read more about the Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection at <https://www.imy.se/otherlang/>

11. APPENDIX 2: METADATA

Sample data	All samples (water, sediment, water filters, leaf litter, etc)	General information	PrID	
			sampleid	
			sample_type	
			watershed	
			latitude	
			longitude	
			habitat	
			country	
			sampling_occasion	
			date	
			owner	
			responsible_person	
			open_access(y/n)	
			nagoya_compliant	
			nagoya_id	
			Observational data	temperature
				pH
	sampling_depth			
	Additional info for water filters	filter_type		
		filtered_material_amount		
	Additional info for leaf litter	species		
		material_type		
	Chemical analysis	sampleid		
substance_concentration				
method				
Extracted DNA	sampleid			
	storage_location			
	extraction_method			
Additional info for archival DNA	responsible_person			
	archive			
	amount			
	date_received			
	processing_timeframe			
Additional info for unspecified sample types	destroy_after_finishing(y/n)			
	material			

		material_amount
		collection_protocol
Sequencing data	Sequence data	accession
		sequence
		source
	Sequencing metadata	accession
		source_version
		approach
		sequencing_platform
		target
		method
		country
	facility	
	Taxonomic data	accession
		kingdom
		phylum
class		
order		
family		
genus		
species		
Personal data	Stakeholders	name
		title
		country
		affiliation
		phone_number
	email_address	
	Partners and teams	name
		affiliation
		country
		email_address
CV		
photo		
social_media_handles		
Photos	author	
	author_contact	
	country	
	date	

12. Document credits & How to cite

How to cite:

Anderson, J. L., Calore, R., Rämä, T., Reñé, A., Prins, V., Ferrari, E., & Woodhouse, J. (2026). MoSTFun Data Management Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18836052>

Photo credits:

Cover: Jason Woodhouse. Provincia di Novara, Italy, 2023.

Visual identity: MoSTFun's visual identity was crafted by Max Fonseca.

Document format and design: Jason Woodhouse and Jennifer Anderson.

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Norway	Teppo Rama	April 2024
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